

CORRECTION

View Article Online

View Journal | View Issue

Cite this: *Inorg. Chem. Front.*, 2019, **6**, 630

Correction: Development of a WS₂/MoTe₂ heterostructure as a counter electrode for the improved performance in dye-sensitized solar cells

Sajjad Hussain,^{a,b} Supriya A. Patil,^{c,d,e} Anam Ali Memon,^{f,g} Dhanasekaran Vikraman,^h Hafiz Ghulam Abbas,ⁱ Sung Hoon Jeong,^f Hyun-Seok Kim,^h Hak-Sung Kim*^{c,d} and Jongwan Jung*^{a,b}

DOI: 10.1039/c8qi90051e

rsc.li/frontiers-inorganic

Correction for 'Development of a WS₂/MoTe₂ heterostructure as a counter electrode for the improved performance in dye-sensitized solar cells' by Sajjad Hussain *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem. Front.*, 2018, **5**, 3178–3183.

The authors regret an error in the affiliations listed for author Anam Ali Memon. The corrected list of author affiliations for this article is shown above.

The authors also regret an error within the Acknowledgements section of the article. The number 2016R1D1A1B01015047 was regrettably omitted. The corrected version of the Acknowledgements section is shown below.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by the Basic Science Research Program through the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF), funded by the Ministry of Education (2010-0020207, 2017R1C1B5076952, 2012R1A6A1029029, and 2016R1D1A1B01015047), by the MOTIE (10052928) and the KSRC (Korea Semiconductor Research Consortium) support programs for the development of future semiconductor devices. This research was also supported by the Korea Institute of Energy Technology Evaluation and Planning (KETEP) and the Ministry of Trade, Industry, and Energy (MOTIE) of the Republic of Korea (20172010106080).

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

^aGraphene Research Institute, Sejong University, Seoul 05006, Republic of Korea. E-mail: jwjung@sejong.ac.kr

^bDepartment of Nano and Advanced Materials Engineering, Sejong University, Seoul 05006, Republic of Korea

^cDepartment of Mechanical Engineering, Hanyang University, 04763 Seoul, Republic of Korea. E-mail: kima@hanyang.ac.kr

^dInstitute of Nano Science and Technology, Hanyang University, Seoul 04763, Republic of Korea

^eDepartment of Energy and Materials Engineering, Dongguk University-Seoul, Seoul 04620, Republic of Korea

^fDepartment of Organic and Nano Engineering, Hanyang University, Seoul 04763, Republic of Korea

^gDepartment of Textile Engineering, Mehran University of Engineering and Technology, Jamshoro Sindh, Pakistan

^hDivision of Electronics and Electrical Engineering, Dongguk University-Seoul, Seoul 04620, Republic of Korea

ⁱDepartment of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, Research Institute of Physics and Chemistry, Chonbuk National University, Jeonju, Chonbuk 54896, Republic of Korea

